

Survey on Requirements for Research Data Management Training (RDMTraining4NFDI)

Introduction

All NFDI consortia are expected to offer training in the knowledge and skills required for research data management (RDM). This training should cover data, software and machine-learning models and be provided to the consortia's own staff, such as data stewards and trainers, as well as to researchers within the respective community. The basic service RDMTraining4NFDI, coordinated by ZB Med - Information Centre for Life Sciences and TH Köln (Technische Hochschule Köln), aims to create a modular collection of foundational RDM training materials together with documented, tried-and-tested training formats and methods. Access to these materials will enable consortia to efficiently develop their own community-specific adaptations of such training and to build capacity quickly. Furthermore, the option of credentialing training materials will be explored as a means of introducing quality standards to training and documenting the skills acquired by participants. In addition, RDMTraining4NFDI provides training on training didactics and aims to test and evaluate diverse training formats to find out how to deliver RDM training most effectively to RDM professionals and data stewards.

This survey, conducted by the basic service RDMT4NFDI, was part of the Base4NFDI project. It sought to better understand the requirements of the NFDI consortia and the wider RDM community on RDM materials, formats and certification. The survey aimed to identify the research data management (RDM) training requirements within the NFDI consortia to better support their needs and to shape this basic service idea. Therefore, the target group were the consortia of the NFDI.

This survey was open from 13.06.2025 until 27.06.2025 and took approximately 10 minutes to answer.

The responses of the survey were only used for internal analysis and service development. Processing was based on the participant's consent (Art. 6(1)(a) GDPR). The survey was conducted using 2ask¹.

Data was stored securely, analyzed only by the RDMT4NFDI team (and if needed, by Base4NFDI² project team), and anonymized before being used in any reports or publications. Consortium names may be published in reports or publications.

¹ provided by orbiz Software GmbH, Robert-Gerwig-Str. 4, 78467 Konstanz. The collected data was handled in accordance with GDPR and was not transferred outside Germany. 2ask used cookies to ensure website functionality and a user-friendly design. For more information, please refer to [2ask's Privacy Policy](#). Please note that this link leads to the provider's website, which may use Google Analytics.

² Base4NFDI is an initiative of all 26 consortia of the NFDI whose consortia assembly selects the proposals for Basic Service development, like RDMT4NFDI, after the Technical Expert Committee reviewed them. The Basic Services are then funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG).

Participants have the opportunity to withdraw the consent or request deletion of their data at any time by contacting rdmtraining4nfdi-orga@lists.nfdi.de.

By completing the survey, the participants confirmed that they had read, understood and accepted this privacy notice.

How to read the Survey

The survey consists of 11 questions and 8 subquestions divided into the following categories: General Information (Q1-3), Trainer Information (Q4, Q7), Materials Information (Q5+6), Training Format Information (Q8+9), Certification Information (Q10) and Service Information (Q11). The survey presents the original questions along with their answer options. Information regarding the type and obligation of each question is provided in brackets after the question.

Questions of the Survey

Q1 General Information: Which type of organisation or project do you primarily represent? If you are affiliated with multiple organisations, please select the one with which you are most actively involved regarding RDM. *(Mandatory, Single Option)*

- University
- University of Applied Sciences (HAW)
- Non-University Research Institution
- Library
- Federal State Initiatives
- Data Competency Center (DKZ)
- Departmental Research
- Other, please specify

Q2 General Information: Which NFDI consortium or consortia do you represent? You may select multiple options if applicable. *(Mandatory, Multiple Options)*

- Base4NFDI (union of consortia)
- BERD@NFDI

- KonsortSWD
- NFDI4Culture
- NFDI4Memory
- NFDI4Objects
- Text+
- NFDI4DataScience
- NFDI4Energy
- NFDI4Ing
- NFDI-Matwerk
- NFDIxCS
- DataPLANT
- FAIRagro
- NFDI4Immuno
- GHGA
- NFDI4Biodiversity
- NFDI4BIOIMAGE
- NFDI4Health
- NFDI4Microbiota
- DAPHNE4NFDI
- FAIRmat
- NFDI4Cat
- MaRDI

- NFDI4Chem
- NFDI4Earth
- PUNCH4NFDI
- Other, please specify
- None

Q3 General Information: Which role best describes your position within your consortium or institution? Choose the one that BEST describes your current role. *(Mandatory, Single Option)*

- Data Steward
- Research Data Management (RDM) Trainer
- Librarian
- Project Manager / Coordinator
- Principal Investigator
- Technical Infrastructure Specialist
- Research Associate in Data Literacy
- Researcher
- Other, please specify

Q4 Trainer Information: Are you delivering/conducting RDM Training actively (at the moment or in the near future)? *(Mandatory, Single Option; if no, jump to Q6, Q7-Q10.1 will be skipped, Q11 - Q11.2 will still be asked)*

- Yes
- No

Q4.1 Trainer Information: How many years of experience do you have in delivering/conducting RDM Training? *(Optional, Single Option)*

- < 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 3-5 years
- > 5 years

Q5 Materials Information: How often do you reuse existing RDM training materials? *(Mandatory, Single Option, if none so far, Q5.2 was skipped)*

- Always
- Most of the time
- Not very often
- None so far

Q5.1 Materials Information: Where do you find/get existing training material or - in case you will be delivering RDM training in the future - where would you be looking for existing training materials? *(Mandatory, Multiple Options, randomized answer options)*

- Training material created in the consortium
- OER platforms (please specify): *(followed by a free text field)*
- AI tools (e.g. ChatGPT)
- Search engines (e.g. Google)
- Reuse of own personal training material
- Other, please specify

I am unsure how to adapt the materials to my domain-specific needs (on a technical level).

I am unsure how to adapt the materials to my domain-specific needs (in terms of transferring the content).

I am unsure how to adapt the learning objectives.

Q6 Materials Information: What do you consider as must-have features for reusable RDM training materials? Please select all that apply: *(Optional, Multiple Options, randomized answer options)*

- Open license (e.g. CC BY)
- Names of authors are listed
- Clearly stated learning objectives
- Clearly stated target audience
- Clearly stated required previous knowledge
- Trainer outline document
- Presentation slides
- Speaker notes
- Trainer script
- Collection of didactic methods
- Regular updates (e.g. once per year)

- Learning objectives test (e.g. test or quiz at the end)
- Modular structure, allowing topic selection
- Do you consider any other features as must-have which were not listed above? If yes, please specify:

Q7 Trainer Information: Did you participate in a RDM Train-the-Trainer workshop that supports you in adjusting and conducting RDM Training?: *(Mandatory, Single Option, if yes, Q7.1 will be skipped; if no, Q8 will be skipped)*

- yes
- no

Q7.1 Trainer Information: If you did not participate in a RDM Train-the-Trainer workshop, please share the reasons: *(Optional, Multiple Options, randomized answer options)*

- I already have sufficient practical knowledge
- No training programs available
- Time constraints
- Cost constraints
- No program with the right content for my needs
- Train-the-trainer programs don't offer the right format
- I could not pick specific modules I was interested in
- No program with a certificate at the end
- Other, please specify

Q8 Format Information: If you participated in a RDM Train-the-Trainer Workshop, which of the following aspects do you want to highlight positively? *(Optional, Multiple Options, randomized answer options)*

- The workshop delivered sufficient practical knowledge

- The workshop included domain-specific parts
- The costs for the workshop were low
- The workshop was conducted online
- The workshop was conducted in person
- The workshop was conducted in a hybrid format
- I could pick the modules that I was interested in
- The workshop had an appropriate duration
- Which aspects are not listed above or which aspects were missing in your course:

Q9 Training Format Information: What format would you prefer in a RDM train-the-trainer workshop? (*Optional, Multiple Options*)

- On-site instructor-led
- Virtual instructor-led
- Self-paced
- Hybrid (self-paced & virtual instructor led)

Q9.1 Training Format Information: What format would you prefer for giving training for the respective domain specific researcher in the consortia? (*Optional, Multiple Options*)

- On-site instructor-led
- Virtual instructor-led
- Self-paced
- Hybrid (self-paced & virtual instructor led)

Reuse of training materials: How to adapt existing materials to fit my specific needs

Certification of RDM training materials (certification of competencies): Establish an RDM certification process within the NFDI

RDM network: Who can I ask for delivering RDM training sessions for specific topics

RDM network: Who I can contact to receive feedback for my RDM training

RDM Trends: Monitoring RDM Trends

Updated training materials: Maintenance and updating of RDM training materials

Q11.1 Service Information: Are there any other areas that you wish support for which were not listed above? (*optional, free text*)

If yes, please specify below:

Q11.2 Service Information: Do you have any comments or suggestions regarding our service for the NFDI consortia? Feel free to share personal ideas, challenges, or needs related to any of the topics mentioned above. (*Optional, Free text*)